

Pneumo-Hydro-Mechanical triple-node zero-thickness cohesive interface element

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Abstract:

A new model for gas transport in water-saturated clays is being developed at TU Delft [1]. This model includes the formation of discrete cracks by the mechanical action of gas pressure. For this purpose, a new type of Pneumo-Hydro-Mechanical (P-H-M) zero-thickness interface element has been formulated and implemented in LAGAMINE. This new element is a “fusion” of two existent types of interface elements already implemented in LAGAMINE, the P-H-M FAIF2 element [2, 3] and the purely mechanical CZMEL element [4]. The new interface element considers practically the same definition of the P-H problem as FAIF2 (Fig. 1), but instead of considering the mechanical problem as a contact problem, it uses a cohesive zone model as in CZMEL.

Figure 1: Definition of the flow problem for a generic species ζ (water or gas) and phase π (liquid or gas).

The new element type has 9 nodes (Figure 2). The nodes on both sides have 4 degrees of freedom (x and y coordinates, water and gas pressure), while the nodes at the mid-plane only have two (water and gas pressure). In contrast with the FAIF2 and CZMEL, interface elements are formally considered in the code as solid elements, i.e. without need of defining “foundation-structure” or “master-slave” binomials.

Figure 2: Nodal degrees of freedom.

The new interface element makes it possible to consider coupled two-phase water-gas flow in cohesive discontinuities, allowing the representation of DGFP in clays, but also other gas or water fracturing processes in geomaterials.

In this presentation, the element formulation and the implementation in LAGAMINE are discussed, as well as some simple benchmark examples to demonstrate the performance of the proposed model.

References:

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